

"TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE: PROFILING LEARNER IDENTITIES AND TAILORING INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES"

Zaripbayeva Nasiba Azamat qizi

Magistrant, Webster universiteti, Tashkent.

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Abstract

The language learning characteristics and instructional philosophies that are relevant to two English language learners at Webster University in Tashkent are examined in this thesis. It looks at the identities, histories, educational requirements, and motivational elements affecting their language learning. The study proposes ways for effective instruction by incorporating pedagogical approaches and theories of second language acquisition. To promote language competency, a focus on establishing encouraging learning settings and attending to the needs of each individual student is made.

1 Introduction

Learning languages is a complicated process that is impacted by many different elements, such as student identities, motives, and teaching methods. This study focuses on two Webster University English language learners to investigate how their distinct identities impact their educational experiences and how individualized teaching approaches can meet their specific needs. Providing insights into efficient teaching methods that accommodate a range of learner characteristics is the aim.

2 Methods

2.1 Participants

For the case studies, two students from Webster University's ESL program were chosen: Nafisa, a Russian speaker, and Ismoil, an Uzbek student with an intermediate level of English competence (B1). The two individuals, whose ages ranged from 18 to 20, had distinct educational backgrounds and objectives.

2.2 Data Collection

Learner interviews, classroom observations, and examination of learners' language competence exams were used to gather data. While interviews examined their motives, learning experiences, and self-perceived problems, observations concentrated on their involvement in language activities.

2.3 Data Analysis

To find themes on learner identities and instructional practices, qualitative analysis was employed. The investigation concentrated on the ways that the motivation and background of each learner affected their language acquisition as well as the effects of individualized instruction on learning outcomes.

3 Results

3.1 Learner Profiles

Ismoil is a tactile and auditory learner who practices her English through volunteer work and social media. His main goal is to study in the United Kingdom. Nafisa is an introverted learner who has studied Korean and Russian. She hopes to become an English teacher by earning an IELTS certification.

3.2 Instructional Strategies

Task-based and communicative language training techniques were among the customized teaching techniques. Role-playing and shadowing activities helped Ismoil improve his phonological abilities. Nafisa profited from collaborative learning settings and self-study materials that fit her introverted personality.

3.3 Motivation and Investment

Ismoil's desire to study in the UK drove him to devote time and resources to his English language education, which enhanced his interest and advancement. Nafisa was motivated to engage in class and make use of extra resources by her ambition to become an IELTS certified teacher and earn her teaching credential.

4 Discussion

4.1 Impact of Learner Identity

The study emphasizes how crucial it is to match teaching tactics to the identities of students. While Nafisa's introverted inclinations necessitated various resources and support, Ismoil's extroverted character and usage of social networks helped his language practice. Their learning results and level of engagement were improved when instruction was adapted to these identities.

4.2 Instructional Implications

A key component of effective language instruction is recognising and meeting the varied requirements of students. Educators ought to utilize an assortment of tactics to cater to varying learning preferences and drives. For example, offering both individualized and interactive learning alternatives can accommodate different student preferences and enhance language acquisition overall.

4.3 Future Research

Additional investigation may be conducted to examine the effects of distinct instructional approaches on different learner profiles in diverse settings. Examining how customized teaching methods affect language proficiency over the long run may shed further light on how best to improve language instruction.

5. Conclusion

Effective language teaching requires an understanding of student identities and the use of customized instructional strategies to address them. This study shows that tailored methods can improve learning outcomes and motivation, which helps diverse learners acquire languages more successfully.

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